

Supplemental Table 1. Structural vulnerability factors* used for database searches and study screening for a scoping review on the association between structural vulnerability factors and gestational weight gain.

Socioeconomic	Ethnic and Cultural	Other
<i>Socioeconomic</i>	<i>Immigrant</i>	<i>Vulnerable</i>
Social / economic	Emigrant	<i>population/group/ person</i>
Social class/stratification/ standing	Refugees	Disadvantage
Social mobility	Asylum seekers	<i>Violence</i>
Disparities	<i>American Native Continental</i>	Domestic/partner
	<i>Ancestry Group</i>	Spousal abuse
<i>Employment</i>	Indians	Physical abuse
Unemployment	Central/North/South	Sexual abuse
Personnel downsizing	American	
Workplace	Inuits/Metis	<i>Marital status</i>
Occupational class	Oceanic Ancestry Group	Family characteristics
	Aboriginals/First Nation/	Divorce/marriage
<i>Economic</i>	Indigenous/Native people	Single
Financial inequality/insecurity		parent/mother/widow
Economic mobility	<i>Ethnic group/minority</i>	
	African American/Canadian	<i>Social support</i>
<i>Income</i>	Asian/Chinese American/	Psychosocial support
Remuneration	Canadian	

Livelihood	Hispanic/Mexican/Latin	Social
Salary	American/Canadian	isolation/alienation/
Impoverished	Arab	Marginalization
<i>Poverty</i>		<i>Sex workers</i>
Poverty areas		Prostitute
<i>Education</i>		<i>Drug users</i>
Literacy/illiteracy		
Poor/low attainment		<i>Adolescence</i>
<i>Health services accessibility</i>		<i>Prisoners</i>
Rural health/ services		
Rural population		<i>Parity</i>
Isolated/secluded/inaccessible region/area/territories		
<i>Food insecurity</i>		

*Structural vulnerability factors were identified based on Bourgois *et al.*'s 2017 conceptual framework (13).